

Subregular Complexity of Tonal Systems: Case Studies of Chinese Languages

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Abstract

Phonological transformations based on finite-state transducers have received an important status since their introduction under the guise of rewrite rules. Finite-state transducers represent regular relations, which are closed under composition. This shows that an apparently complex system of phonological rules can be compiled into a single finite-state transducer. On the other hand, regular relations are still too powerful as a probable upper bound of the complexity of phonological transformations. For example, regular relations are able to encode such a phonological transformation that only applies to an even number of terms, obviously unattested as an adequate rule.

Recently, studies of the so-called subregular classes, that is, classes even weaker than regular relations, have proved to be a more probable upper bound. Such classes are conceptualized as a hierarchy, not unlike the traditional Chomsky hierarchy in formal language theory. The remaining problem is how many phonological phenomena are explainable and, more importantly, NOT explainable by each class. In this inquiry, tonal systems post an interesting challenge, and thus require a more in-depth investigation.

Traditionally, tonal systems are accounted for by nonlinear phonology, which involves the use of multiple phonological tiers and their associations. This process can be carefully separated into two ideas:

1. Tones can be independently represented on a separate tier just as segments do;
2. The associations between phonological tiers can be manipulated in a nontrivial way.

In this thesis, the two ideas are examined under the lens of attested tonal systems found in Chinese languages with vastly different tonal transformations. Their implication applies not only to tonal systems, but also to the interfaces between linguistic levels in general.

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1 Theoretical Background

This chapter introduces the theoretical foundations needed for the interpretation of tonal systems. The theories are presented from two perspectives, namely theoretical and computational phonology, which utilize different methodologies. Although this thesis uses a computational approach, the theoretical implication requires an understanding of relevant approaches as well.

Specifically, the focus is placed on phonological TRANSFORMATIONS as opposed to PHONOTACTICS. Their distinction corresponds to the distinction between transducers and acceptors in automata theory, which reflect translation and membership problems respectively. Loosely speaking, a transducer is a function of type $\alpha \rightarrow \beta \rightarrow \text{Boolean}$, while an acceptor of type $\alpha \rightarrow \text{Boolean}$, that is, a predicate.¹² The latter will be briefly mentioned as the theories are introduced.

Given the theoretical background, this chapter then explains the rationales behind the chosen methodology as well as the expected results. In particular, this thesis has the goal of clarifying the unique operations on autosegmental representations that empower them to account for certain tonal transformations.

1.1 Theoretical Phonology

This section details the presentations of phonological transformations in theoretical phonology. Phonological transformations have been employed by two allegedly divergent formalisms, often named linear and nonlinear phonology. As explained in the later section on the computational perspective, this categorization fails to recognize the actual properties that render computationally more complex formalisms necessary. Nonetheless, this section will follow the traditional categorization.

This section also discusses the organization of grammar. As will become clear once computational models are introduced, organization only matters in the compositions of phonological transformations, contrary to the common conception that cyclicity and ordering are inherent properties of phonological systems. Lexical phonology is mentioned for its significance in the arguments against cyclicity.

The discussion of OPTIMALITY THEORY as in Prince & Smolensky (1993) is intentionally omitted. The reason is not that optimality theory is a worse formalism, but merely that its

¹For deterministic transducers, the types are isomorphic to $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$.

²Unless a gradient interpretation of phonology is required, in which case the output type can be, for example, an interval type.

formalization results in computational devices out of the scope of this thesis. Specifically, optimality theory, due to its constraint-optimizing nature, requires constraint optimizers rather than transducers, which are potentially powerful enough to overgenerate. For such an implementation based on dynamic programming, refer to Tesar (1995). For discussions of the computational complexity of optimality theory, refer to Eisner (1997), Idsardi (2006), and Heinz, Kobele & Riggle (2009), among others.

1.1.1 Linear Phonology

The earliest discussion of phonological transformations dates back to Chomsky & Halle (1968), where rules are in the form of context-sensitive rewrite rules. For example, a vowel nasalization rule can be in the form

$$(1.1) \quad V \rightarrow [+nasal] / __ [+nasal]$$

read as ‘nasalize a vowel immediately before a nasal sound’. Under the usual notation of rewrite rules, this is written as

$$(1.2) \quad V[+nasal] \rightarrow (V \cup [+nasal])[+nasal]$$

understood as ‘rewrite a vowel immediately before a nasal sound to the union of the vowel and the singleton set of the nasal feature’. It should be noted that this apparently context-sensitive form is by no means actually context-sensitive. What it means is that, given the Chomsky hierarchy (Chomsky 1959)

$$(1.3) \quad \text{Recursively enumerable} \supset \text{Context-sensitive} \supset \text{Context-free} \supset \text{Regular}$$

it is not true that phonological transformations form a superset of context-free relations. This is shown in the later section on regular relations.

Attention should be paid to ‘linear’. One interpretation is that phonological transformations apply to a linear sequence of segments. This assumes that segmental phonology, the sort that is dealt with above, is disjoint from nonsegmental phonology. This assumption is computationally unsound, as nonsegmental phonology does not necessarily require a ‘nonlinear’ account, and conversely segmental phonology may require one. Another interpretation has to do with the notion of locality, which is an often misunderstood notion in theoretical phonology.

A relevant concern is the representations of tonal features. Indeed, due to the ‘linear’ nature of the representations, tonal features have nowhere else to fit in but the same feature sets as the segmental features. Consider, for example, Wang’s (1967) interesting characterization of Xiamen tone cycle:

$$(1.4) \quad [\alpha \text{ high}, \beta \text{ fall}] \rightarrow [\beta \text{ high}, -\alpha \text{ fall}]$$

This rule not only uses the same FORM as segmental rules, but also the same REPRESENTATION. Of course, it is not a problem if the rule explains the tone cycle well.³ On the other hand, a nonlinear account allows more freedom both in the form and representation of the rule. Readers are thus reminded that representation is a separate matter from the computational complexity of the formalism INDEPENDENT of representation.

1.1.2 Nonlinear Phonology

Despite the remarks made above, nonsegmental phonology is precisely what has inspired the development of nonlinear phonology, also known as autosegmental phonology. Early applications of nonlinear phonology can be found in Clements (1976) and Goldsmith (1976), among others. Under nonlinear phonology, phonological representations consist of multiple associated tiers, each tier with its own linear sequence of terms. For example, a syllable [ma] with a high level tone can be represented as

where σ stands for a syllable and H stands for a high tone. Consequently, phonological transformations are generalized to operate on associations. An unbounded tone spreading rule can be given as:

An implicit assumption is that the rule applies iteratively from left to right. This intuition is, surprisingly, captured equally well by linear transformations. An equally acceptable formulation is the linear transformation

(1.7) $T\varepsilon\varepsilon \rightarrow TT\varepsilon \rightarrow TTT$

where ε stands for the empty term, assuming the transformation also applies iteratively from left to right.

The pair of examples above suggests that the power of nonlinear phonology comes not from the representations, nor from the capability of iterative application. Instead, it comes from the

³See, however, Chen's (2000) criticism of the characterization.

ability to encode the associations in the transformations, as explicated by the computational models. Iterative application, on the other hand, concerns the computational nature of the rules, which is reflected by the mappings their corresponding process produces.

A point should be made that iterative application has little to do with the organization of grammar. An iteratively applied phonological transformation is neither inherently associated with cyclicity nor with ordering. In fact, it is not necessarily iterative at all under an alternative representation. The only thing relevant is the PROCESS the rule generates as embodied by the equivalent computational device.

1.1.3 Organization of Grammar

What organization of grammar concerns is, then, NOT the computational nature of phonological transformations, but rather the use of linguistic formalisms to express computationally equivalent models.⁴ This is reminiscent of the use of programming paradigms to express computationally equivalent programs given their Turing completeness, except we expect a much weaker upper bound in phonological models.

The concept of CYCLICITY, that is, repeatedly applying a phonological transformation until it is no longer applicable, played an important role in early formulations of nonsegmental phonology. The idea is that a series of rules is linearly sequenced as R_1, \dots, R_n , where R_n is a rule that creates new contexts for the previous rules, often conceived as a ‘bracket erasure’ rule. This brings two problems:

1. The end result of rule applications is tightly coupled with how contexts are represented;
2. It is not clear how to apply different sequences of rules at each level of representation.

The former is hardly an inherent or unique problem of cyclicity. The latter, in comparison, is a more serious problem, as it prohibits an otherwise modular organization of grammar by the virtue of ‘rules bloat’. Alternatively, LEXICAL PHONOLOGY advocates for a ‘stratified’ approach (Kiparsky 1982), thus achieving a more modular organization. This thesis adopts the general approach of lexical phonology without assuming any form of the lexicalist hypothesis.

The ORDERING of phonological transformations, on the other hand, is a more universal problem. Even simply modeling phonological transformations as functions already leads to the ordering problem, as

$$(1.8) \quad \neg(\forall f, g. f \circ g \Rightarrow g \circ f)$$

That is, function composition is noncommutative. Therefore, this thesis does not expect this problem to be easily solved.

⁴This is not to deny that linguistic formalisms differ in their expressivity in a nontrivial manner. Expressivity and computability are orthogonal, as the famous ‘Turing tarpit’ analogy puts it (Perlis 1982).

1.2 Computational Phonology

This section introduces computational formalization of phonological transformations in terms of regular relations, in particular subregular functions. The main method of computationally formalizing phonological transformations concerns the use of machines in the sense of automata theory. In particular, finite-state machines are used for their limited computational complexity. They are able to encode regular relations, but not context-sensitive or even context-free relations due to their lack of a stack.

Logical encodings of regular relations are also introduced along with their transductions. Encoding regular relations in terms of logical formulae facilitates the understanding of their subparts as compared to transducers and enables the evaluation of their computational complexity as first-order, quantifier-free, among others.

1.2.1 Regular Relation

The apparently context-sensitive phonological rules have the important constraint that all terms are `TERMINAL`, that is, not able to be further rewritten into themselves, directly or indirectly. As Chomsky (1959) points out, the distinguishing feature of context-free languages is exactly the ability to self-embed, which requires recursively rewriting `NONTERMINAL` terms into themselves preceded and followed by other terms. Formally, a grammar is self-embedding iff

$$(1.9) \quad \exists A, \varphi, \psi. A \rightarrow^+ \varphi A \psi$$

where neither φ nor ψ is the identity term and \rightarrow^+ is the transitive closure of the rewrite relation. Clearly, phonology does not permit such a structure. Kaplan & Kay (1994) therefore suggests modeling phonological transformations as `REGULAR` relations.

Regular relations are relations whose domains and ranges are regular languages. An artificial regular relation, for example, is a relation that rewrites any sequence that has an `EVEN` number of a to a sequence with each a replaced by b . This is an unattested phonological transformation, but it is a valid regular relation, showcasing that regular relations are still computationally too complex for modeling phonological transformations.

Regular relations can be represented as the equivalent `FINITE-STATE` transducers. Finite-state transducers are machines that transit between a finite number of states according to the currently read term, where transitions emit the output terms. To put it another way, `ACCEPTORS` are machines that accept `ONE` sequence of terms, while `TRANSDUCERS` are ones that accept `TWO` sequences of terms, namely the input and output sequences. The artificial regular relation above requires a `NONDETERMINISTIC` finite-state transducer that either rewrites a to b or does not, whose validity is only determined after the whole input sequence is read:

This artificial regular relation is unattested, which means the transducer overgenerates. Ideally, two additional constraints are desired:

1. The transducers be DETERMINISTIC to exclude multiple outputs;
2. The transducers be LOCAL to limit the required memory resource.

These two constraints, in turn, lead to subregular functions.

Alternatively, regular relations can be represented as logical transductions, specifically MONADIC SECOND-ORDER ones as those in Engelfriet & Hoogeboom (2001), which are actually able to represent nonregular relations.⁵ Monadic second-order logic allows quantification over sets, which is needed for the definition of general precedence $<$ based on immediate precedence $<_a$:⁶

$$(1.11) \quad \begin{aligned} \text{a. } & \textit{Transitive}(X) := \forall x, y. (x \in X \wedge x < y) \Rightarrow y \in X \\ \text{b. } & x < y := \forall X. (x \in X \wedge \textit{Transitive}(X)) \Rightarrow y \in X \end{aligned}$$

This is understood as ‘ x precedes y iff every transitive set with respect to immediate precedence that includes x also includes y ’, which means the transitive closure also includes y . A relation is then defined that expresses that an a immediately precedes another a ignoring any non- a between them:

$$(1.12) \quad x <_a y := a(x) \wedge a(y) \wedge x < y \wedge \neg(\exists z. a(z) \wedge x < z \wedge z < y)$$

The notion of the evenness of the number of a is finally defined:

$$(1.13) \quad \begin{aligned} \text{a. } & \textit{Odd}(x) := (a(x) \wedge (\forall y. y < x \Rightarrow \neg a(y))) \vee (\exists y. \textit{Even}(y) \wedge y <_a x) \\ \text{b. } & \textit{Even}(x) := \exists y. \textit{Odd}(y) \wedge y <_a x \end{aligned}$$

Accordingly, the transduction is defined:⁷

⁵An example is the first-order definable total reduplication $w \rightarrow ww$, whose output language is included in the class of tree-adjointing languages (Shanker & Weir 1994).

⁶This is to assume the relations are nonrecursive.

⁷Observant readers may notice that an efficient transducer implementing said transduction reads the input TWICE, dispatching on the number of a in the first pass. This is due to the correspondence between monadic second-order logic and two-way finite-state transducers.

$$(1.14) \quad b'(x) := b(x) \vee (a(x) \wedge (\exists y. \text{Even}(y) \wedge (\forall z. y < z \Rightarrow \neg a(z))))$$

Similar to how finite-state transducers are constrained, logical transductions of the sort above are avoided if

- Quantification over sets is disallowed; or
- Any quantification is disallowed.

They result in FIRST-ORDER logic and its QUANTIFIER-FREE version respectively, which correspond to various subregular functions.

Despite their inadequate computational complexity, regular relations are useful as they are closed under composition, meaning that

$$(1.15) \quad \forall P, Q. (\text{Regular}(P) \wedge \text{Regular}(Q)) \Rightarrow \text{Regular}(P \circ Q)$$

This enables the possibility to compile an apparently complex system of phonological rules into a single finite-state transducer.

1.2.2 Subregular Function

The most trivial class of SUBREGULAR functions is without a doubt the class of finite functions, which is disfavored in this thesis for the reasons mentioned in Savitch (1993). Rather, by enforcing the aforementioned constraints, several nontrivial classes of subregular functions can be subdivided. If the finite-state transducers are required to be deterministic, the resulting subregular functions are SUBSEQUENTIAL functions, further classified into left and right variants depending on the direction the input sequence is read (Chandlee & Heinz 2012, Heinz & Lai 2013). This class is not particularly interesting for the purposes of this thesis, as it lacks a meaningful notion of locality.

The concept of STRICT LOCALITY is defined for regular languages, which concerns the recognition of substrings (Rogers & Pullum 2011, Rogers et al. 2013). Borrowing this concept, input and output strictly local functions can be defined over LINEAR representations, which ‘remember’ a finite length of input and output substrings respectively (Chandlee, Eyraud & Heinz 2014). Similar to subsequential functions, output strictly local functions can be further classified into left and right variants (Chandlee, Eyraud & Heinz 2015).

An example of input strictly local function is the function that rewrites a to b whenever the last input is a . That is,

$$(1.16) \quad a^{n+1} \rightarrow ab^n$$

where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, with the equivalent transducer

where the remembered input term is encoded in the state. More conveniently, it can also be represented as the logical transduction

$$(1.18) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } a'(x) := a(x) \wedge \neg(a(\text{pred}(x))) \\ \text{b. } b'(x) := a(x) \wedge a(\text{pred}(x)) \end{array}$$

where pred is the predecessor function.

Similarly, an example of left output strictly local function is the function that rewrites a to b whenever the last output is a . That is,

$$(1.19) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } a^{2n} \rightarrow (ab)^n \\ \text{b. } a^{2n+1} \rightarrow (ab)^n a \end{array}$$

with the equivalent transducer

where the remembered output terms are encoded in the states. When it is represented as a logical transduction, however, there occurs RECURSIVE logical formulae,⁸ resulting in a recursive strictly local function:

$$(1.21) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } a'(x) := a(x) \wedge \neg(a'(\text{pred}(x))) \\ \text{b. } b'(x) := a(x) \wedge a'(\text{pred}(x)) \end{array}$$

As Chandlee & Jardine (2021) conjectures, recursive logical transductions comprise precisely the logical characterization of output strictly local functions.

Logical encodings enable the generalization of strict locality over AUTOSEGMENTAL representations (Chandlee & Jardine 2019a). Under a predicate logic, associations are understood as a binary relation Assoc where $\text{Assoc}(a, b)$ indicates that a and b are associated, where a and b are on separate tiers.⁹ For example, the unbounded tone spreading rule can be defined as the recursive logical transduction

$$(1.22) \quad \text{Assoc}'(x, y) := \text{Assoc}(x, y) \vee \text{Assoc}'(x, \text{pred}(y))$$

Is it then easy to see why it works equally well for linear representations. Assoc is merely used to represent the presence of tones:

⁸Readers familiar with fixed-point theorems may expect to see a fixed-point logic undermining such recursive logical formulae. The technical details can be found in Koser, Oakden & Jardine (2018) and Chandlee & Jardine (2019b).

⁹A question can be asked whether Assoc is symmetric. Although this question has no particular bearing, Assoc is assumed to be antisymmetric to allow the interpretation of autosegmental representations as directed graphs.

- (1.23) a. $T(x) = \exists y. Assoc(y, x)$
 b. $T'(x) = \exists y. Assoc'(y, x)$

This makes it possible to surject the autosegmental transformation into a linear one:

- (1.24) a. $T'(x) := T(x) \vee T'(pred(x))$
 $Assoc'(a, x) = Assoc(a, x) \vee Assoc'(a, pred(x))$
 b. $\frac{(\exists y. Assoc'(y, x)) = (\exists y. Assoc(y, x) \vee Assoc'(y, pred(x)))}{(\exists y. Assoc'(y, x)) = ((\exists y. Assoc(y, x)) \vee (\exists y. Assoc'(y, pred(x))))}$
 $T'(x) = T(x) \vee T'(pred(x))$

In other words, the linear transformation is EMBEDDED. The existential introduction reflects the fact that the transformation only cares about the EXISTENCE of any term on the tonal tier that is associated with the input term.

Strictly local logical tranductions, as shown thus far, satisfy both first-orderness and quantifier-freeness. This is not a coincidence, but rather the expected outcome. By disallowing quantification, logical formulae are allowed to refer to terms other than the input terms only by the means of the predecessor and successor functions, which in turn allude to the notion of locality.

1.3 Preliminary Goal

Chinese languages have been famous for their rich repertoire of tonal systems and relevant transformations. In particular, tonal transformations in Chinese languages often interact with the morphosyntactic representations. This fact has inspired analyses that require morphosyntactic encodings in phonological representations. This thesis expects to formulate such techniques in terms of strictly local functions.

Another question this thesis aims to answer is why autosegmental representations appear necessary. Indeed, as later shown, autosegmental representations impose the requirement that phonological representations be graphs as opposed to linear sequences of terms. This question is impossible to answer without assessing what autosegmental representations are useful for.

Finally, this thesis attempts to supply a theoretical interpretation of the computational analyses. The theoretical implication of strictly local functions, this thesis believes, is more general than the study of computational complexity. Potentially, it relates to the more difficult problem of the interfaces between linguistic levels. A complete answer to this question requires a better understanding of the primitives and operations each level allows.

2 Boundary of Transformation

With the computational preliminaries in place, we are now ready to analyze the attested tonal transformations found in Chinese languages. This chapter specifically discusses transformations involving boundaries that can block the applications. Despite the simple facets of transformations *per se*, the existence of boundaries raises certain important questions, such as where, when, and how they come into play. This is especially problematic under linear models, as hierarchical interpretations of boundaries often require more than linear sequences.

2.1 Representation of Boundary

The linear understanding of BOUNDARIES is simply certain terms that never surface, yet block any transformation that may otherwise apply. A boundary term is always output AS IS, therefore failing to satisfy any condition when it precedes or succeeds the input term in question. Consider again the unbounded tone spreading rule:

$$(2.1) \quad \acute{\sigma}'(x) := \acute{\sigma}(x) \vee (\sigma(x) \wedge \acute{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(x)))$$

A boundary term certainly cannot satisfy $\sigma(x)$, and thus $\acute{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(x))$ cannot be true when it precedes the input term. This quickly fails to account for more complicated rule interactions, where boundaries may CHANGE to create new contexts. Recall that cyclicity assumes that each cycle creates new contexts until fixed point—this intuition leads to analyses that delete and insert new boundaries.

An alternative view of boundaries is GROUPINGS, which can render the transformation nonregular. Even if we ignore this nature of arbitrary groupings by restricting self-embedding in some manner, there is still the issue of determining whether two terms are in the same group. Suppose groupings are delimited by conventional brackets, to determine whether two terms are in the same group, the transducer potentially needs to traverse the whole input sequence. This is more apparent in the case of autosegmental representations, where groupings are represented as trees, which are a subset of directed graphs.¹ The relation that decides whether two terms are in the same group is then

$$(2.2) \quad \text{SameGroup}(x, y) := \exists z. \text{Assoc}(z, x) \wedge \text{Assoc}(z, y)$$

assuming that groupings do not nest. As usual, nestable groupings require the transitive closure of *Assoc*, which is monadic second-order definable.

¹Such trees with a limited depth are known as ‘prosodic hierarchy’, for which see Nespor & Vogel (1986).

If we entirely discard the idea of explicitly encoding boundaries in input sequences, we need to derive the same processes as before, thereby implicitly encoding boundaries in some sense. What boundary terms achieve is essentially applying a single transformation to multiple linear sequences and combining the outputs through some associative operation, say concatenation. In other words, the transformation is ‘lifted’ to operate on multiple linear sequences. By doing so, we modularize the transformation into a simpler transformation and a universal lift operation.²

However, groupings are much different, as they create input TREES. Input trees, by their inductive nature, can contain more trees, which are in turn input trees to a potentially new transducer with appropriate hierarchical notions encoded. It not only generates a recursive process, but also creates a leaky abstraction as the transducer must be aware of the whole input up to a certain level. This defeats the purpose of having multiple linguistic levels in the first place.

The ideal scenario is that each linguistic level drives phonological realization by feeding the next level inputs and combining the outputs. This eliminates the need of boundaries altogether, while implicitly preserving their essence. This is also much what cyclicity really aims to achieve, namely that each cycle further transforms the input sequence with one layer of groupings removed. What this means in practice will be demonstrated in the following sections as relevant linguistic data are covered.

2.2 Standard Chinese: Tone 3 Sandhi

Tone 3 sandhi is a tonal transformation found in Standard Chinese, where tone 3 is dissimilated to tone 2 before another tone 3. This process can be described as simultaneously applied, as seen in the following data:

- (2.3) a. *zhǎnlǎn* → *zhánlǎn* ‘exhibit’
 b. *zhǎnlǎnguǎn* → *zhánlǎnguǎn* ‘exhibition hall’
 c. *zhǎnlǎnguǎn lǐ* → *zhánlǎnguǎn lǐ* ‘in exhibition hall’

Therefore, a logical transduction

$$(2.4) \quad \acute{\sigma}'(x) := \acute{\sigma}(x) \vee (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}(\text{succ}(x)))$$

resulting in the mapping

$$(2.5) \quad \check{\sigma}^{n+1} \rightarrow \acute{\sigma}^n \check{\sigma}$$

²This operation is precisely a functor, or loosely speaking function of type $(\alpha \rightarrow \beta) \rightarrow \mathbb{F}\alpha \rightarrow \mathbb{F}\beta$, commonly known as *map*. \mathbb{F} should produce a type whose values can be ‘folded’ in the sense of Hutton (1999) under a monoid.

should be enough to describe the process. It should be emphasized that this process is linear in its computational nature, REGARDLESS of the specific representation used here for convenience. Indeed, even if the tones are represented on a separate tier with multiple terms, the transformation is still linear and, importantly, strictly local, albeit with a larger memory size.³ Namely, the mapping will then be

$$(2.6) \quad (LL)^{n+1} \rightarrow (LR)^n LL$$

ignoring the optional alternative realization of tone 3 when it is lengthened (Duanmu 1999). The fundamental reason is that the associations are not affected by the transformation, that is, *Assoc* is never mentioned in the transduction.

The transformation becomes more interesting when boundaries are concerned. The data

- (2.7) a. *gǒu bǐ mǎ xiǎo* → *góu bǐ má xiǎo*
 b. *gǒu bǐ mǎ xiǎo*
 dog than horse small
 ‘Dogs are smaller than horses.’

show that certain tone 3 does NOT change to tone 2. This seems to suggest that an alternative transduction

$$(2.8) \quad \acute{\sigma}'(x) := \acute{\sigma}(x) \vee (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \acute{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x)))$$

resulting in the mapping

- (2.9) a. $\check{\sigma}^{2n} \rightarrow (\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma})^n$
 b. $\check{\sigma}^{2n+1} \rightarrow \check{\sigma}(\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma})^n$

is in effect. This is not true, as the data

- (2.10) a. *xiǎogǒu bǐ xiǎomǎ xiǎo* → *xiǎogóu bǐ xiǎomá xiǎo*
 b. *xiǎo-gǒu bǐ xiǎo-mǎ xiǎo*
 small-dog than small-horse small
 ‘Puppies are smaller than ponies.’

clearly do not adhere to the mapping. Moreover, the data

- (2.11) a. *xiǎo zhǐlǎohǔ* → {*xiǎo zhǐláohǔ*, *xiǎo zhǐláohǔ*, *xiǎo zhǐláohǔ*}
 b. *xiǎo zhǐ-lǎohǔ*
 small paper-tiger
 ‘small paper tiger’

³To decide the memory size, it suffices to calculate the number $n + m$, where n and m are respectively the highest degrees of composition of the predecessor and successor functions in the normalized transduction.

show that certain tone 3 OPTIONALLY changes to tone 2. To account for such contrasts, various analyses have been developed. Two such analyses will be discussed, where one is representative for ‘syntactic’ analyses and the other for ‘prosodic’ analyses.

2.2.1 Syntactic Analysis

Chen (2000) argues for a analysis under which feet are built based on syntactic structures, which in turn govern the application of tone 3 sandhi. As Duanmu (2007) states, Although this analysis includes a notion of feet, they are nonetheless not related to prosody given their insensitivity to stress. More crucially, the tone 3 sandhi rule makes reference to the syntactic structure for the applicability. Therefore, it is considered a ‘syntactic’ analysis here.

The basic idea is that syntactic branching leads to different foot structures. For example, a left branching syntactic structure leads to a left foot:

- (2.12) a. (*mǎi hǎo*) *jiǔ* → (*mái háo*) *jiǔ*
 b. [[*mǎi hǎo*] *jiǔ*]
 buy good wine
 ‘to finish buying wine’

Tone 3 sandhi applies to *mǎi* as it is followed by another tone 3 syllable in the same foot. The curious part is *hǎo*, which is followed by another tone 3 syllable in a HIGHER group. A right branching syntactic structure, on the other hand, leads to a right foot:

- (2.13) a. *mǎi (hǎo jiǔ)* → {*mǎi (háo jiǔ)*, *mái (háo jiǔ)*}
 b. [*mǎi* [*hǎo jiǔ*]]
 buy good wine
 ‘to buy good wine’

Tone 3 sandhi now only optionally applies to *mái*, as it is followed by another tone 3 syllable in a LOWER group. Apparently, this implies that nestable groupings are required. As aforementioned, nestable groupings lead to monadic second-order logic over TREES, which is an undesirable property.

Alternatively, we may consider that the trees be transformed to linear sequences suitable as inputs to the later level. This can be a simple recursive process that flattens the input trees using an associative operation that prefixes boundaries.⁴ This tree transformation can be nondeterministic to account for the optionality, but the level it feeds, tone 3 sandhi, remains deterministic.⁵ Considering only the nontrivial cases, we have

⁴This process can also be represented as a strictly local tree transducer, as linear sequences are isomorphic to single-pathed graphs, that is, unary-branching trees. See Ikawa, Ohtaka & Jardine (2020) and Ji & Heinz (2020) for detailed discussions of such transducers.

⁵Under nondeterminism, an output sequence that contains a *ǒǒ* substring simply fails and backtracks. Although Chen (2000) reports several data that contain such substrings, they are more likely due to emphatic stresses.

In some sense, this is as if only opening brackets were preserved. Syntactic categories are insignificant, as the process only makes reference to the hierarchical structure. This, of course, still requires modification to tone 3 sandhi, as now the input sequences contain boundaries. To completely suppress boundaries in the inputs, we can further split linear sequences by boundaries, resulting in multiple linear sequences.⁶ Tone 3 sandhi is then lifted to operate on these linear sequences, whose outputs are combined by concatenation. To put it simply, this means that

(2.15) a. $\#v\#wz \rightarrow \tau(v) \cdot \tau(w \cdot z)$
 b. $\##vwz \rightarrow \tau(v \cdot w \cdot z)$

omitting empty sequences. Interestingly, the contrast now comes from the fact that tone 3 sandhi does not preserve concatenation:

(2.16) $\neg(\forall x, y. \tau(x \cdot y) = \tau(x) \cdot \tau(y))$

If this DID hold, we would be able to derive the equivalence of the two mappings due to associativity.

A note should be made regarding cyclicity. In Chen's (2000) original analysis, cyclicity is used to explain both simultaneous and optional applications, on the assumption that groupings can be expanded at each level. However, we have seen how cyclicity is NOT an essential property of the analysis by virtue of modularization, where a tree transformation feeds tone 3 sandhi.

2.2.2 Prosodic Analysis

Duanmu (2007) proposes an alternative analysis in light of several perceived inadequacies of the previous syntactic analysis. The most significant one is that supposedly same syntactic structures can lead to different groupings, as

⁶Or, obviously, transform to multiple linear sequences in a single pass. The presentation is merely for easier understanding under a graph-transduction perspective.

(2.17) (něizhǒng) (jiǔ hǎo) → (néizhǒng) (jiú hǎo)

must be derived from

(2.18) [[[něi-zhǒng] jiǔ] hǎo]
 which-kind alcoholic.beverage good
 ‘Which kind of alcoholic beverage is good?’

supposing the syntactic structure is correct at all. This obviously hinges on specific syntactic analysis, as one can imagine

(2.19) [[[něi-zhǒng] [__ jiǔ]] hǎo]
 which-kind GAP alcoholic.beverage good
 ‘Which kind of alcoholic beverage is good?’

being a totally valid alternative analysis that DOES derive the correct grouping.⁷ With the addition of gap terms, the tree transformation requires more elaboration, but this does not change the computational nature of the linear transformation. Similarly, some other provided data can arguably be attributed to alternative syntactic analyses.

Another perceived inadequacy is the insensitivity to stresses, which is the reason behind the name ‘stress-insensitive foot’. For example, an emphatic stress as in

(2.20) xiǎng (MǎI gǔpiào) → xiǎng (MǎI gǔpiào)

seems to favor (force?) a boundary before the emphasized syllable. Again, this only requires modification to the tree transformation. Nonetheless, Duanmu (2007) opts for a more aggressive modification to both the tree transformation and tone 3 sandhi.

Under the proposal, syntactic trees are assigned stresses according to the ‘information-stress principle’, which covers syntactic structures assuming that nonheads carry more information. The syllables are then grouped into feet based on stresses, where a stressed syllable must start a group. As these feet are considered metrical due to the relevance of stresses, the analysis is a prosodic one.

The complication is that tone 3 sandhi must be aware of BOTH the syntactic structure and prosodic groupings due to the way ‘adjacency’ is defined. Two syllables are said to be ‘adjacent’ when they are contained by the same syntactic constituent and not by separate full feet, where a full foot is a grouping with more than one syllable. This notion must be defined over autosegmental representations:

(2.21) a. $Adjacent(x, y) := SameConst(x, y) \wedge \neg SepFullFeet(x, y)$
 b. $SameConst(x, y) := \exists z. Dom(z, x) \wedge Dom(z, y)$

⁷Justification for a similar analysis based on type shifting can be found in Barker & Shan (2014), which generalizes to all determiners.

- c. $SepFullFeet(x, y) := \exists z, w. z \neq w \wedge FullFeet(z, x) \wedge FullFeet(w, y)$
d. $FullFeet(x, y) := Feet(x, y) \wedge (\exists z. Feet(x, z) \wedge (prec(y) = z \vee succ(y) = z))$

Dom is the transitive closure of the syntactic association relation, and *Feet* is the prosodic association relation. This is overcomplicated as a phonological process, at least from our point of view.

Moreover, tone 3 sandhi is now said to be a nondeterministic process, which optionally changes tone 3 before nonadjacent or sandhi tone 3. In a logical world, this can be achieved by an operator that introduces choice points, say McCarthy's (1961) *amb* operator:

- (2.22) a. $\acute{\sigma}'(x) := \acute{\sigma}(x) \vee (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}(succ(x)) \wedge \neg MaybeSkip(x))$
b. $MaybeSkip(x) := amb(\neg Adjacent(x, succ(x)), \check{\sigma}(succ(succ(x))), \perp)$

We see how convoluted the analysis becomes once the phonological process is no longer subregular. Even though tone 3 sandhi is one of the simplest phonological processes, the CONDITION it applies heavily depends on syntactic information. Still worse, its application can be nondeterministic. By distributing the workload to tone 3 sandhi, its computational nature is effectively obscured. Moreover, using autosegmental representations to represent HIERARCHICAL structures is in some sense an abuse.

2.3 Tianjin Mandarin: Rule Interaction

Tianjin Mandarin is a more interesting case than Standard Chinese, as there are a total of THREE tone sandhi rules that interact in a nontrivial way. In Tianjin Mandarin, three dissimilation rules similar to tone 3 sandhi in Standard Chinese are found:⁸

- (2.23) a. $\grave{\sigma}\grave{\sigma} \rightarrow \check{\sigma}\grave{\sigma}$ (F[alling-]F sandhi)
b. $\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}$ (L[ow-]L sandhi)
c. $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma} \rightarrow \bar{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$ (R[ising-]R sandhi)

These rules approximately generalize to trisyllabic sequences in a manner reminiscent of directionalities:

- (2.24) a. $\grave{\sigma}\grave{\sigma}\grave{\sigma} \rightarrow \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\grave{\sigma}$ (right-to-left)
b. $\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}$ (right-to-left)
c. $\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma} \rightarrow \bar{\sigma}\bar{\sigma}\acute{\sigma} \rightarrow \bar{\sigma}\bar{\sigma}\bar{\sigma}$ (left-to-right)

There has been debates on how these rules interact and, more importantly, how to explain such interactions. Rule-based analyses such as Tan's (1987) and Zhang's (1987) proposals rely

⁸For convenience, notations borrowed from Hanyu Pinyin are used to indicate the tones, although they do not phonologically correspond to the specific tones in Standard Chinese.

on stipulations to account for the directionalities as well as the feeding relations, therefore offering no real explanation. In the subregular zoo, instead of directionalities, the difference in patterns amounts to the difference in logical formulae, that is, the computational nature of the rules. The problem is then how to also accommodate the feeding relations. A relevant ‘boundaryless’ computational analysis will be discussed before a new ‘boundaryful’ analysis is presented.

2.3.1 Bounadaryless Analysis

Chandlee’s (2018) analysis is based on the observation that the three strictly local functions can be combined into a single one, which must remember a pair of input and output substrings. It is thus an input–output strictly local function. Following our convention so far, the idea will be described using logical formulae instead of transducers. The logical transduction, without consideration of the feeding relations, is as follows:

$$(2.25) \quad \begin{aligned} \text{a. } \check{\sigma}'(x) &:= (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \neg \check{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \vee (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \\ \text{b. } \acute{\sigma}'(x) &:= (\acute{\sigma}(x) \wedge \neg \acute{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \vee (\acute{\sigma}(x) \wedge \acute{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \\ \text{c. } \bar{\sigma}'(x) &:= \bar{\sigma}(x) \vee (\acute{\sigma}(x) \wedge \acute{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \end{aligned}$$

In the transduction, rule interactions are naturally derived from the shapes of logical formulae. We see that FF sandhi feeds LL sandhi given the presence of $\check{\sigma}'$, and similarly that LL sandhi counterfeeds RR sandhi given the absence of $\acute{\sigma}'$. A redefinition of the transduction gives us another possibility:

$$(2.26) \quad \begin{aligned} \text{a. } \check{\sigma}'(x) &:= (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \neg \check{\sigma}^\wedge(\text{succ}(x))) \vee (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \\ \text{b. } \acute{\sigma}'(x) &:= (\acute{\sigma}(x) \wedge \neg \acute{\sigma}^\vee(\text{succ}(x))) \vee (\acute{\sigma}(x) \wedge \acute{\sigma}^\wedge(\text{succ}(x))) \\ \text{c. } \bar{\sigma}'(x) &:= \bar{\sigma}(x) \vee (\acute{\sigma}(x) \wedge \acute{\sigma}^\vee(\text{succ}(x))) \\ \text{d. } \check{\sigma}^\wedge(x) &:= \check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(x) \\ \text{e. } \acute{\sigma}^\vee(x) &:= \acute{\sigma}(x) \vee \acute{\sigma}'(x) \end{aligned}$$

FF sandhi now counterfeeds LL sandhi given the presence of $\check{\sigma}^\wedge$, that is, a sandhi low tone does NOT trigger LL sandhi. Likewise, LL sandhi now feeds RR sandhi given the presence of $\acute{\sigma}^\vee$, that is, a rising tone either in the input or output sequence triggers RR sandhi.

This analysis apparently does not make reference to boundaries, unlike our analysis of tone 3 sandhi in Standard Chinese. This leads a difficulty in describing the conflicting data:

$$(2.27) \quad \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$$

The former alternative suggests that FF sandhi counterfeeds LL sandhi, while the latter suggests otherwise:

$$(2.28) \quad \text{a. } \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}$$

$$b. \quad \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}$$

The presence of the extra step of application is exactly what differentiates counterfeeding and feeding, at least given the lack of boundaries. Unfortunately, we can encode either counterfeeding or feeding, but not both. The contrast of the two, nonetheless, is analogous to the situation in Standard Chinese. Indeed, the following holds assuming FF sandhi feeds LL sandhi:

$$(2.29) \quad \begin{array}{l} a. \quad \tau(\check{\sigma}) \cdot \tau(\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}) = \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \\ b. \quad \tau(\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}) = \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \end{array}$$

2.3.2 Boundaryful Analysis

The data shown in Tan (1987) are actually subject to a clear contrast between left-branching and right-branching structures, which we now know derive different boundaries. The most trivial case of boundaries is found when every syllable is emphatically stressed, thus creating the sequence

$$(2.30) \quad v\#w\#z$$

that does not undergo any sandhi. This happens since a single syllable can not be affected by the transduction, namely that

$$(2.31) \quad \tau(v) \cdot \tau(w) \cdot \tau(z) = vwz$$

This is not particularly interesting, but does show that boundaries are in effect. This case is henceforth ignored for lack of interest.

The more interesting cases are found when some syllables do undergo sandhi. In these cases, Tianjin Mandarin uses a more ‘conservative’ approach to creating boundaries, such that every constituent receives a prefix and suffix boundary when flattened. This leads to the tree transformation

that appears as if every bracket is rewritten into a boundary term. In other words, when boundaries are outputted at all, a left-branching structure causes the substring of first two syllables to undergo tone sandhi, while a right-branching one does that of last two. As usual, the tree transformation is nondeterministic so that boundaries are allowed to be omitted.

With this in mind, it is still true that the patterns that are attested for BOTH left-branching and right-branching structures can be used to justify the trisyllabic generalization, as these patterns occur when boundaries are omitted. The transduction therefore remains strictly local, while the originally conflicting data can now be well explained:

$$(2.33) \quad \check{\sigma}(\sigma\check{\sigma}) \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}, \sigma\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$$

Applying this idea to more data shows that it is indeed the right track. The cases of trisyllabic sequences are shown first, as these cases do not involve the complication of feeding relations:

$$(2.34) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \check{\sigma}(\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}) \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}, \check{\sigma}\sigma\check{\sigma}\} \\ \text{b. } (\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma})\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \{\sigma\check{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}, \check{\sigma}\sigma\check{\sigma}\} \\ \text{c. } \sigma(\sigma\sigma) \rightarrow \{\sigma\#\bar{\sigma}\sigma, \bar{\sigma}\bar{\sigma}\sigma\} \\ \text{d. } (\sigma\sigma)\sigma \rightarrow \{\bar{\sigma}\sigma\#\sigma, \bar{\sigma}\bar{\sigma}\sigma\} \end{array}$$

The FF sandhi data also suggest a minor modification to the transduction to accommodate the rule

$$(2.35) \quad \sigma\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \bar{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \quad (\text{FL sandhi})$$

that produces the following mappings:

$$(2.36) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \sigma\sigma\sigma \rightarrow \bar{\sigma}\sigma\sigma \\ \text{b. } \sigma\sigma\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \check{\sigma}\bar{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \end{array}$$

This can be done by redefining the logical transduction:

$$(2.37) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \check{\sigma}'(x) := (\check{\sigma}(x) \wedge \neg\check{\sigma}^\wedge(\text{succ}(x))) \vee (\sigma(x) \wedge \sigma(\text{succ}(x)) \wedge \neg\check{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \\ \text{b. } \bar{\sigma}'(x) := \bar{\sigma}(x) \vee (\sigma(x) \wedge \sigma^\vee(\text{succ}(x))) \vee (\sigma(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(\text{succ}(x))) \end{array}$$

The interaction is a curious one, as now FF sandhi feeds FL sandhi WHILE counterbled by it. This is rather complicated to describe with cyclicity, but simple enough as a strictly local function. Correct patterns of FF sandhi can now be predicted:

$$(2.38) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \sigma(\sigma\sigma) \rightarrow \{\sigma\#\check{\sigma}\sigma, \bar{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\sigma\} \\ \text{b. } (\sigma\sigma)\sigma \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\sigma\#\sigma, \bar{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\sigma\} \end{array}$$

To decide the feeding relations, data involving rule interactions are examined:

- (2.39) a. LL sandhi bleeds FL sandhi
 (i) $\acute{\sigma}(\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}) \rightarrow \{\acute{\sigma}\#\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$
 (ii) $(\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma})\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$
 b. FL sandhi counterbleeds FF sandhi
 (i) $\acute{\sigma}(\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}) \rightarrow \{\acute{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}, \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$
 (ii) $(\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma})\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}, \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$
 c. LL sandhi feeds RR sandhi
 (i) $\acute{\sigma}(\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}) \rightarrow \{\acute{\sigma}\#\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}, \check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$
 (ii) $(\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma})\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \{\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}, \check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\}$
 d. FF sandhi feeds LL sandhi
 (i) $\check{\sigma}(\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}) \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\#\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\}$
 (ii) $(\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma})\acute{\sigma} \rightarrow \{\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\#\acute{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\}$

All that remains is a transduction that is compatible with all cases, which can be defined using the shown techniques.

Lastly, some rare cases in the data seem to suggest that LL sandhi produces the alternative mapping:

$$(2.40) \quad \check{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\check{\sigma} \rightarrow \acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}$$

As previously discussed, adding alternatives to the transduction incurs nondeterminism. Instead, it is more likely that some lexical items with a low tone have alternative realizations with a rising tone, moving nondeterminism out from the transduction.⁹

2.4 Interim Summary

This section has argued for a modular analysis of tonal transformation that is sensitive to the hierarchical structure. The point is not to suggest that a certain analysis is inherently better than another. Rather, it argues that such a modular analysis is computationally feasible and clarifies the boundaries between linguistic levels. Even if the overall complexity of the composed system remains the same, a modular analysis allows for the local reasoning of each module due to abstraction and encapsulation.

Specifically, a boundary-based analysis is presented for both Standard Chinese and Tianjin Mandarin, where a boundary is merely a term that blocks the transformation. In this sense, the whole transformation can be understood as a boundary-agnostic subtransformation ‘lifted’ to operate on multiple linear sequences that are produced by splitting the input sequence by boundaries. This is how we achieve modularity—by further and further separating out each step of computation and composing them together at the end.

⁹This can also explain the mapping $\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\acute{\sigma} \rightarrow \acute{\sigma}\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}$ even if counterfeeding is assumed.

The theoretical implication is that the methodological assumption of lexical phonology or any modular approach in general is preferable. Nonetheless, this does not and should not bear any substantive implication. Nothing is assumed about the ‘architecture of the language faculty’, as this issue is simply not important in the computational understanding of phonology. We agree with lexical phonology inasmuch as both are opposed to the cyclic and thus monolithic view of phonology. Anything more is left aside.

3 Power of Representation

In the previous chapter, we have had a taste of how representations can obscure the computational nature. This chapter relates this intuition to even more attested tonal transformations. Representations are indispensable both as a theoretical tool and metatheoretical notion, and they often enforce specific ways to express the computation. Choosing an incorrect representation can either overly simplify or complicate the computation, much to our dismay.

3.1 Representation as Computation

Representations, when considered as a part of bigger computation, implicitly ENCODE partially or fully done computation. This is not new to linguists, as syntacticians often face the dichotomy between features and constraints, whose equivalence is pointed out in Graf (2017). The contentious issue of enriched representations has also been a long-standing problem in theoretical phonology.

Most significantly, choosing an unintuitive representation can lead to a seemingly simplified computation, at the expense of a more complex conversion from the intuitive representation. A famous example is how de Bruijn's (1972) notation highly simplifies substitution in λ -calculus by eliminating variable shadowing, despite the fact that the conversion from a conventional notation requires taking care of exactly that! As another example, recall the unattested transformation that rewrites a depending on the evenness of its number. Suppose the representation encodes this information by splitting a into \acute{a} and \grave{a} , with the following constraints:

- (3.1)
- a. $\acute{a}(x) \Rightarrow (\forall y. x < y \Rightarrow \neg \grave{a}(y))$
 - b. $(\acute{a}(x) \wedge (\neg \exists y. x \triangleleft_a y)) \Rightarrow \text{Odd}(x)$
 - c. $\grave{a}(x) \Rightarrow (\forall y. x < y \Rightarrow \neg \acute{a}(y))$
 - d. $(\grave{a}(x) \wedge (\neg \exists y. x \triangleleft_a y)) \Rightarrow \text{Even}(x)$

The transformation then simply rewrites each \acute{a} to a and \grave{a} to b . All is well, except now the representation not only encodes the evenness information, but also renders many sequences invalid. It is only reasonable when it serves as an INTERMEDIATE representation that encodes the decision of the evenness. Even then, the decision would have had the same computational complexity as before anyway.

More surprisingly, representations can also complicate the computation, in particular when the structures are unsuited for the problem domain. The familiar issue of cyclicity is precisely one example, as it essentially leads to a hierarchical structure in phonology. This hierarchical

structure, in turn, creates the important question of conditions of application, which is one of the reasons regular models were adopted in Kaplan & Kay (1994). Conversely, the fact that arbitrary term rewriting generates recursively enumerable languages as proved by Peters & Ritchie (1973) suggests that a more principled ‘movement’ theory is required, ideally based on hierarchical structures. Nowadays, variants of categorial grammars such as combinatory categorial grammars in Steedman (2000) are adopted.

The mention of categorial grammars relates to a fundamental issue in our metatheory. Our metatheory is inherently a logical one, partially due to its ease of understanding, but more so due to the equational reasoning provided by logical calculi. A CALCULUS, in essence, is a theory of the equivalence between representations, defined ‘up to’ some relations. By studying the calculus directly or indirectly, we gain a better understanding of the essential properties in the formalisms, in contrast to idiosyncratic artifacts of our metalanguage. For example, λ -terms that differ only in bound variable names are equivalent up to α -equivalence, suggesting that names should not matter. In the case of subregular functions, the logical transductions are their defining property, as opposed to the theoretically inspired representations.

3.2 Shanghai Wu: Tone Spreading

Shanghai Wu has a tonal transformation traditionally known as ‘left dominance’, properly named so after the fact that the leftmost syllable decides the tonal pattern of the whole group. Detailed theoretical discussions can be found in Duanmu (1993, 1999) among others. This tonal transformation is particularly relevant as it is often analyzed as an AUTOSEGMENTAL phenomenon, despite its almost linear nature.

Intuitively, the idea is that the first term on the tonal tier is always associated with the first syllable, while the second term is associated with either the first or second syllable depending on whether the latter is present. The remaining syllables, if any, remain unassociated with any term and are thus ‘toneless’. This gives us the following mappings:

It is worth it to ask whether autosegmental representations are really needed. For example, it is not apparent why the excessive terms on the tonal tier should be present at all if they always end up unused by the transformation. A bigger problem is that the tonal status of a specific

syllable is always tied to the association relation, forcing us to retreat to this unnecessary indirection and obscuring the nature of left dominance.

To demonstrate the effects of this theoretical assumption of autosegmental representations, an autosegmental analysis proposed by Zhu (2020a) will be discussed, followed by our linear analysis. As we will see, there is little to no reason to assume autosegmental representations, at least in the case of Shanghai Wu. It is in some sense overly generalized, contra the spirit of pinning down the exact computational complexity, as well as creating the problem of normalized representations.

3.2.1 Autosegmental Analysis

Zhu's (2020a) analysis is a 'port' of the theoretical analysis to the computational land. It is argued that left dominance CANNOT be a linear transformation based on the assumption that a contour tone consists of multiple tonal terms. Indeed, a hypothetical linear transformation involving n tonal terms seems to require a memory size of n , as

$$(3.3) \quad T_1 T_2 \dots T_{n-1} T_n \rightarrow T_1 T_2$$

must remember T_2 up to T_n , crossing the syllabic boundary. This assumption, of course, deserves further questioning. Regardless, the proposed analysis defines the transduction as

$$(3.4) \quad \text{Assoc}'(x, y) := (\text{First}(x) \wedge \text{First}(y) \wedge \text{Assoc}(x, y)) \vee \\ (\text{Second}(x) \wedge \text{Second}(y) \wedge \text{Assoc}(x, \text{pred}(y)))$$

where *First* and *Second* are predicates that test whether the term is the 'first' or 'second' term. They can be defined as follows assuming left dominance applies to #-separated units:

$$(3.5) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \text{First}(x) := \#(\text{pred}(x)) \\ \text{b. } \text{Second}(x) := \neg\#(\text{pred}(x)) \wedge \#(\text{pred}(\text{pred}(x))) \end{array}$$

Similarly, a predicate *Last* that tests whether the term is the 'last' term can be defined, which will become useful later:

$$(3.6) \quad \text{Last}(x) := \#(\text{succ}(x))$$

This transduction does not generate the exact mapping we are looking for. Instead, it generates

$$(3.7) \quad \begin{array}{ccccccc} \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots & \rightarrow & \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots \\ | & \diagdown & & & | & | & \\ T & T & T \dots & & T & T & T \dots \end{array}$$

This imposes an undesirable assumption of the ‘underlying’ association, even though it never surfaces in this specific mapping. Supposedly, the assumption is made to account for the trivial case of monosyllabic sequences, where the mapping is

$$(3.8) \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \sigma & \rightarrow & \sigma \\ \diagdown & & \diagdown \\ \text{T} & \text{T} & \text{T} \quad \text{T} \end{array}$$

that is, an identity map. The transduction, however, does not reflect this intuition of ‘citation’ forms, as

$$(3.9) \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \sigma & \rightarrow & \sigma \\ \diagdown & & | \\ \text{T} \quad \text{T} \quad \text{T}\dots & & \text{T} \quad \text{T} \quad \text{T}\dots \end{array}$$

does not preserve the underlying association.

Upon further examination, *Assoc* appears to be unnecessary in the transduction. A re-definition of the transduction can drop the reference to it, as the surface association merely depends on the POSITIONS of the terms:

$$(3.10) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \text{Assoc}'(x, y) := (\text{First}(x) \wedge \text{First}(y)) \vee (\text{Second}(x) \wedge (\text{Only}(y) \vee \text{Second}(y))) \\ \text{b. } \text{Only}(x) := \text{First}(x) \wedge \text{Last}(x) \end{array}$$

This transduction directly corresponds to the theoretical analysis and assumes nothing about the underlying association. This gives rise to the question whether the ‘garbage’ tonal terms are retained in the surface forms—if a normalization procedure is in effect. Intuitively, the surface forms should always be normalized to encode the LEAST information as possible. Such normalization can be achieved by tailoring the domain predicate that decides whether or not a term is copied:¹

$$(3.11) \quad \text{Copy}(x) := \neg \text{T}(x) \vee \text{First}(x) \vee \text{Second}(x)$$

A more severe problem is that this transformation misses the *yánggrù* pattern. This pattern occurs when the first syllable both starts with a voiced onset (‘*yáng*’) and ends with a stop coda (‘*rù*’), and is much different from the above pattern:

$$(3.12) \quad \begin{array}{ccc} \sigma & \sigma\dots & \sigma \\ \rightarrow & & \rightarrow \\ \sigma & \sigma\dots & \sigma \\ \diagdown & & \diagdown \\ \text{T} & \text{T} \quad \text{T}\dots & \text{T} \quad \text{T} \quad \text{T}\dots \end{array}$$

¹And, accordingly, the predecessor and successor functions are adjusted to the domain.

In this sense, syllabic boundaries are NOT needed in the inputs at all, as they can be created by another transformation:

$$(3.18) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \cdot'(x) := \text{Second}(x) \wedge \neg \text{Last}(x) \\ \text{b. } T'(x) := \text{First}(x) \vee \text{Last}(x) \vee \text{Second}(\text{pred}(x)) \end{array}$$

Unfortunately, the *yánggrù* pattern does not show an apparent correspondence to linear representations of this kind. The major problem is that the use of syllabic boundary above is not for delimiting units, but rather as a ‘diacritic’ to mark the alternative configuration. This falls down for the *yánggrù* pattern, as there are now n configurations where $n \in \mathbb{N}$, echoing with the original argument against linear transformation.

Alternatively, we can resort to a strictly one-to-one association between syllables and tones, that is, marking the tones on the syllables. In fact, the tonal patterns in Shanghai Wu are limited to these four types, where the first two types are accounted for by the classical analysis of left dominance:³

$$(3.19) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \text{a. } \{\hat{\sigma}, \acute{\sigma} \grave{\sigma} \dots\} & (\text{yīnpíng}) \\ \text{b. } \{\check{\sigma}, \grave{\sigma} \acute{\sigma} \dots\} & (\text{shǎngqùshēng}) \\ \text{c. } \{\acute{\sigma}, \grave{\sigma} \acute{\sigma} \dots\} & (\text{yīnrù}) \\ \text{d. } \{\check{\sigma}, \grave{\sigma} \grave{\sigma} \dots \check{\sigma}\} & (\text{yánggrù}) \end{array}$$

First, consider a linear transformation that accounts for the non-*yánggrù* patterns. Following the intuition that the monosyllabic sequences reflect some sort of ‘citation’ forms, the tones are left unchanged when they are on the only syllables:

$$(3.20) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \hat{\sigma}'(x) := \text{Only}(x) \wedge \hat{\sigma}(x) \\ \text{b. } \check{\sigma}'(x) := \text{Only}(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}(x) \end{array}$$

In polysyllabic cases, the first two syllables have their tones decided by the first syllable:

$$(3.21) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \acute{\sigma}'(x) := \\ \quad (\text{Only}(x) \wedge \acute{\sigma}(x)) \vee \\ \quad (\text{FirstNonLast}(x) \wedge \hat{\sigma}(x)) \vee \\ \quad (\text{Second}(x) \wedge (\check{\sigma}(\text{pred}(x)) \vee \acute{\sigma}(\text{pred}(x)))) \\ \text{b. } \grave{\sigma}'(x) := (\text{FirstNonLast}(x) \wedge (\check{\sigma}(x) \vee \acute{\sigma}(x))) \vee (\text{Second}(x) \wedge \hat{\sigma}(\text{pred}(x))) \\ \text{c. } \text{FirstNonLast}(x) := \text{First}(x) \wedge \neg \text{Last}(x) \end{array}$$

The remaining syllables are assigned neutral tones:

$$(3.22) \quad \sigma'(x) := \neg(\text{First}(x) \vee \text{Second}(x))$$

³Tones are indicated as in the International Phonetic Alphabet.

The above transformation, like its autosegmental counterpart, is nonrecursive. However, the *yángrù* pattern still requires a recursive definition given that it is characteristically a tone spreading rule:

$$(3.23) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \check{\sigma}'(x) := \text{FirstNonLast}(x) \vee (\neg \text{Last}(x) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(x))) \\ \text{b. } \check{\sigma}'(x) := \text{Last}(x) \end{array}$$

The combination of the two transformations, again, requires the distinction between the *yángrù* and non-*yángrù* patterns. The same technique can be adapted to the linear transformation, with the caveat that tone spreading applies up to the PENULTIMATE syllable. The resulting transduction is as follows, omitting predicates that carry their original definitions:⁴

$$(3.24) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } \check{\sigma}'(x) := \\ \quad (\text{Only}(x) \wedge (\check{\sigma}(x) \vee \text{Yángrù}(x))) \vee \\ \quad (\text{Last}(x) \wedge \\ \quad ((\text{Second}(x) \wedge \text{Yángrù}(\text{pred}(x))) \vee (\check{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(x)) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(\text{pred}(x))))) \\ \text{b. } \acute{\sigma}'(x) := \\ \quad (\text{FirstNonLast}(x) \wedge (\check{\sigma}(x) \vee \acute{\sigma}(x) \vee \text{Yángrù}(x))) \vee \\ \quad (\text{Second}(x) \wedge \hat{\sigma}(\text{pred}(x))) \vee \\ \quad (\neg \text{Last}(x) \wedge \\ \quad ((\text{Second}(x) \wedge \text{Yángrù}(\text{pred}(x))) \vee (\check{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(x)) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(\text{pred}(x))))) \\ \text{c. } \sigma'(x) := \neg(\text{First}(x) \vee \text{Second}(x) \vee (\check{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(x)) \wedge \check{\sigma}'(\text{pred}(\text{pred}(x))))) \end{array}$$

The last predicate reflects the fact that neutral tones only surface after a ‘contour’ formed by the first two syllables.

The combined linear transformation surprisingly resembles its autosegmental counterpart to some degree, except that more concrete tonal representations are used. This is not a coincidence, but merely a result of the general idea of left dominance. An implementation of this idea necessarily involves the distinction between *yángrù* and non-*yángrù*, as well as that between monosyllabic and polysyllabic.

On the other hand, the autosegmental transformation is an OVERGENERALIZATION. It is in some sense not a tonal transformation, but an ‘association transformation’, since it does not assume anything about the tonal terms. There is therefore nothing stopping, say, $\check{\sigma}\acute{\sigma}\sigma$... from being a valid surface pattern given LLT... on the tonal tier, while the linear transformation does not acknowledge the $\check{\sigma}$ predicate at all. Normalization is also not a problem in the linear transformation, as each tone is strictly marked on each syllable, whereas the autosegmental transformation does not care much beyond the association relation.

⁴For convenience, *yángrù* is assumed to be a unique tone in the inputs, although such an assumption does not otherwise change the overall complexity, as *yángrù* can be recognized by the segmental features.

3.3 Suzhou Wu: Exceptional Pattern

Suzhou Wu is similar to Shanghai Wu in that left dominance patterns can be found in some heavy-initial sequences, where ‘heavy’ refers to syllables that do not end with a stop coda. Following Zhu’s (2020b, 2023) theoretical analysis, there are five types for such syllables:

- (3.25) a. ti^{HH} ‘low’ (yīnpíng)
 b. $dí^{LH}$ ‘carry’ (yángpíng)
 c. ti^{HL} ‘bottom’ (yīnshǎng)
 d. ti^{HLH} ‘emperor’ (yīnqù)
 e. $dí^{LHL}$ ‘ground’ (yángshǎngqù)

Specifically, *yángpíng*- and *yángshǎngqù*-initial sequences show an obvious pattern of left dominance as in the autosegmental mapping:

$$(3.26) \quad \begin{array}{ccccccc} \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots & \rightarrow & \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots \\ & & & & | & | & \\ & & & & L & H & (L) \end{array}$$

The same mapping applies to *yīnpíng*-initial sequences assuming that the mapping is only sensitive to the associations. However, *yīnshǎng*-initial sequences undergo a different mapping where the first syllable always bears the same tone:

$$(3.27) \quad \begin{array}{ccccccc} \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots & \rightarrow & \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots \\ & & & & | \diagdown & & \\ & & & & H & L & \end{array}$$

The second syllable can be assumed to either associate with the second tonal term or remain unassociated. Either way, it surfaces with a low tone.

To account for the contrast between left-dominant and ‘exceptional’ patterns, a proposal based on the idea of ‘floating tones’ has been introduced. Basically, the transformation must now be sensitive to the underlying association such that only the unassociated tonal terms are subject to the left-dominant mapping. By doing so, the transformation is able to produce both mappings:

$$(3.28) \quad \begin{array}{ccccccc} \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots & \rightarrow & \sigma & \sigma & \sigma \dots \\ & & & & | & | & \\ T & T & T \dots & & T & T & T \dots \end{array}$$

It is therefore natural to ask how such a transformation can be computationally implemented. A relevant computational analysis found in Zhu (2020a) will be discussed and criticized due to its mischaracterization of the computational complexity, contrasted with our analysis. The idea of ‘diacritical’ features will be mentioned and justified.

3.3.1 Morphemic Analysis

Zhu’s (2020a) analysis of Suzhou is a ‘morphemic’ analysis in the sense that it involves the addition of an extra morphemic tier on top of the existing segmental and tonal tiers. As a result, *yángpíng* and *yīnshǎng* syllables are represented as

Curiously, the morphemic association relation Rel_{Mor} serves no apparent purpose in the transduction. Indeed, the transduction is defined as

$$(3.30) \quad Assoc'(x, y) := ((Assoc(x, y) \vee First(x)) \wedge First(y)) \vee (\neg Assoc(x, pred(y)) \wedge (\exists z. Rel_{Mor}(z, y) \wedge First(z)) \wedge Second(x) \wedge Second(y))$$

where Rel_{Mor} causes the unfortunate presence of existential quantification. In Zhu (2020a), this existential quantification is left out from the transduction, resulting in its mischaracterization as strictly local. This cannot be true, as the transduction must be logically closed, while the removal of the existential quantification leads to a free variable. Regardless, this transduction produces the following mappings:

As the very least, we can consider how to preserve the intuition of the transduction while removing the unnecessary assumptions. An immediate note to make is that the addition of Rel_{Mor} contributes nothing to the transduction whatsoever. It is introduced purely on a theoretical basis, much like what we have seen in the case of Shanghai Wu. Crucially, it disambiguates the cases where a floating tone can be either from the first or second syllable:

Nonetheless, there is the possibility that such a distinction is simply UNFEASIBLE given that existential quantification is needed to make use of the morphemic information. In fact, it is rather reminiscent of the problem of grouping previously discussed. Moreover, this scenario does not appear in Suzhou Wu, not even when ‘light’-initial sequences are concerned.

Another problem is that the transduction is forced to assume that the relevant tonal terms for exceptional patterns must always be underlyingly associated with the first syllable. This

This transduction *SEEMS* to be simpler. However, it is exactly equivalent to the transduction based on underlying association. To justify this fact, consider that the two diacritical features are complementary, that is,

$$(3.37) \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{a. } T^1(x) = \neg T^2(x) \\ \text{b. } T^2(x) = \neg T^1(x) \end{array}$$

Viewed this way, it is very much like subcategorization as used in the odd–even transformation. Therefore, an alternative definition for our transduction is

$$(3.38) \quad \text{Assoc}'(x, y) := ((T^1(x) \vee \text{First}(x)) \wedge \text{First}(y)) \vee (\neg T^1(x) \wedge \text{Second}(y))$$

In some sense, underlying association is an alternative encoding for this diacritical feature:

$$(3.39) \quad T^1(x) = (\exists y. \text{Assoc}(x, y)) \wedge \text{Second}(x)$$

To put it another way, the diacritical feature is *EMBEDDED* as underlying association. This reflects the intuition that exceptional patterns only occur when the second tonal term is not a floating tone. The difference is whether such a notion is encoded as a predicate or binary relation. Either way, the previous transformation that feeds tone sandhi must be sensitive to the types of the first syllable that lead to exceptional patterns.

As we have seen, the many-to-one nature of autosegmental representations is unavoidable precisely due to the use of binary relations. Binary relations are convertible to predicates through quantification, but doing so essentially creates a surjection, that is, many-to-one mapping. Linear representations, on the other hand, avoid the problem altogether due to the lack of binary relations. Our purpose is not to argue for one representation over the other, but merely to emphasize the essential properties of each representation.

3.4 Interim Summary

A recurring debate in theoretical linguistics is the nature of the primitives in our theories. It is often assumed that there is a fundamental difference between, say, privative and binary features. From a computational point of view, the primitives *PER SE* are really meaningless, and only their behaviors matter. In this section, the two systems in question are linear and autosegmental representations.

Indeed, what makes autosegmental representations special is their extra power brought by the association relation, not the fact that tonal features can be decomposed into multiple terms. If the autosegmental transformation can be proved to be equivalent to a linear transformation, linear representations can as well be used with no loss in power. In particular, autosegmental representations require phonotactic constraints to verify the well-formedness, and such constraints are very much equivalent to a transformation to linear representations.

Ironically, more aggressive theoretical proposals have been proposed that decompose segmental features into multiple terms, such as Kaye, Lowenstamm & Vergnaud (1985), but only the autosegmental treatment of tonal features is widely accepted. These autosegmental proposals are all subject to the abovementioned problem in that phonotactic constraints are required. In this sense, linear representations simplify the computation by implicitly encode these constraints, revolving to our original point.

4 Conclusion

This chapter summarizes and discusses the findings of this thesis. The comparison between the computational and theoretical approaches to phonology is presented, followed by future prospects that aim to extend on the findings. See also the interim summaries of the previous chapters for the theoretical interpretations.

4.1 Computation vs. Theory

There is admittedly a gap between computational models and theoretical proposals. Computational phonology, at least the school that this thesis is a part of, focuses on characterizing each phonological phenomenon in terms of computational devices with as few assumptions as possible. Theoretical phonology, on the other hand, strives for a more elegant and unified explanation of each phonological phenomenon. This leads to strong, often too strong, assumptions made by theoretical proposals.

Is this an irreconcilable conflict between the two approaches? This thesis is obviously not enough to provide a decisive answer to this question. Nonetheless, what we see in the case studies is that the intuition of theoretical proposals can often be preserved even if we drop some of the assumptions. This is one of the aims of this thesis, that is, to fit the theoretical proposals in the computational world.

To some degree, the computational approach also echoes with the idea of ‘conspiracy’ à la Kisseberth (1970). Optimality theory has been successful precisely because it provides a way to derive phonological phenomena with few assumptions, namely a constraint optimizer parameterized by a set of constraints. The computational approach assumes equally as few, namely a transducer parameterized by a set of logical relations or equivalently a set of transitions.

4.2 Future Prospect

Type Theory Following Howard’s (1969) ‘formulae-as-types’ conception, logical formulae correspond to types, and by extension logical calculi correspond to type systems. For example, logical conjunction $p \wedge q$ corresponds to product types $\alpha \times \beta$, logical disjunction $p \vee q$ corresponds to sum types $\alpha + \beta$, and logical implication $p \Rightarrow q$ corresponds to function types $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$. Given the heavy use of logical formulae in this thesis, one naturally wonders whether it can benefit from a type-theoretic characterization of transducers.

A type-theoretical approach can potentially lead to a more structured characterization of phonological transformation by enriching the types. At the moment, the input and output

types are simply graph types, specifically single-pathed graphs in the case of linear sequences. This means that a large subset of graphs are impossible as either input or output, resulting in partial functions. By reflecting this fact in the type, we ‘make illegal states unrepresentable’ as per the catchy slogan, therefore avoiding partial functions.

What is Interface? Interface is an often referenced but seldom defined concept. From a computational perspective, an INTERFACE defines what information can be communicated between two levels. The two levels must interact in such a manner that respects the interface, which forces us to clearly state what each level does. However, we have seen that some theoretical proposals entangle morphosyntax and phonology, contradicting this understanding of interface.

Recently, advances in theoretical morphology have brought to us several ‘decompositional’ theories, such as Halle & Marantz’s (1993) distributed morphology and Caha’s (2009) nanosyntax. A computational study of them will hopefully improve our understanding of the morphosyntax–phonology interface, especially in contrast to ‘process-based’ theories such as Anderson (1992).

Wishful Thinking This thesis adopts a ‘wishful thinking’ that all defined logical transductions actually made sense. Keen-eyed readers will notice that some of them are neither input nor recursive strictly local, where both the input and recursive predicates use either the predecessor or successor function. This thesis wishes that such logical transductions made sense by conjecturing that they correspond to input–output strictly local functions. Whether this is true and how this extends to autosegmental representations remain unanswered.

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